

Factors Impeding Excellence in the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Full Service Schools in Matlosana Local Education Office

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to outline factors hindering the implementation of inclusive education in full service schools in Matlosana local education office. The study aims to provide national, provincial and district support teams with the impediments that negatively affected successful implementation of inclusive education in schools. The second aim was to bring about maximum support to schools that needed support to cater the needs of learners with learning barriers. The secondary school educators were made participants. Members of school based support team were also selected as teachers implementing inclusive education. Data was collected using semi-structured interviews which were administered to a stratified sample of primary and secondary school teachers.

The data was gathered from the participants and analysed in thematic manner. The results indicated that the implementation of inclusive education was hampered by various issues such as inappropriate implementation of Screening identification and assessment and support (SIAS) policy, lack of functionality of School based support team (SBST), lack of teacher training, teachers failing to apply for learner concession and accommodation and placement.

Keywords:- Full Service Schools, Inclusive Education, Impediments To Inclusive Education, Learners With Education Special Needs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inclusive classroom as a learning environment that has learners of various abilities, skills and knowledge. It usually means that “learners with special educational needs are in the same class along with ‘regular’ learners” (Zulch, 2010:12), thus signifying that learners learn to get along, how to allow more ‘wait time’ for an answer and how to be more tolerant of other learners.

Since the implementation of inclusive education in South Africa there has been numerous challenges that hinders the successful implementation of inclusive education. Inclusive education as was introduced as a results of Salamanca conference held in Spain 1994, having bone of

contention to curb disparity experience prior 1994 where learners with learning barriers were ignored.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There has been a concern that most learners in South African school especially those who are said to be with learning barriers are not catered are unintentionally and intentionally ignored. Numerous researchers have also made it clear that there are several impediments that hinders the successful implementation of inclusive education in full service schools. Sijuola, Rasaan & Davidova, Jelena. (2022).

➤ *The impediments to excellent implementation of inclusive education*

- Lack of implementation of SIAS policy in schools
- The functionality and the composition of SBST
- Insufficient teacher in-service training
- Inadequate support materials
- Lack of curriculum adjustment

The prevalent of the above stipulated impediments are witnessed in most full service schools around Matlosana local education office. Screening identification and assessment support policy is the policy that was introduced after Salamanca conference held in Spain 1994, Salamanca Statement and framework for Action on Special Needs Education (UNESCO, 1994) with the intention to respond to the need in a consistent and standardised way in addressing the needs of learners with learning barriers. To improve access to quality education for vulnerable learners and those who experience barriers to learning, including:

- Many learners are found to be failing in mainstream schools as they are not catered for.
- Learners cannot cope in the mainstream schools as they are not fully supported i.e. those who are identified with learning disabilities.

The process of identifying, assessing and enrolling learners in special schools and in settings where they can receive support, will be overhauled and replaced by structures that acknowledge the central role played by teachers and parents, Education White Paper 6 (2001).

The diagram below outlines the purpose and stages to be followed in the implementation of successful inclusive education in full service schools.

Fig 1: Purpose of the SIAS Policy

Fig 2. SIAS CYCLE: Processes to be followed in implementing SIAS policy.

The above diagram stipulate all the processes to be taken when implementing SIAS policy with the intention of alleviating impediments to the implementation of inclusive education in inclusive school.

➤ *Research questions:*

- What are factors impeding the excellence in the implementation of inclusive education in Matlosana schools.
- How schools with learners with learning barriers may be supported to enhance maximum participation and results.

➤ *Purpose of the study:*

- To outline factors impeding the excellence in the implementation inclusive education.
- How learners with learning barriers in inclusive schools will be supported.

➤ *Population sampling selection of participants:*

Participants in the study includes teachers from one secondary school in Matlosana and learners from such schools in Matlosana. Members from school based support team were also selected as people working directly with learners with learning disabilities.

Lastly, two members of SMT from each selected schools will form part of the interviews. The SMT is selected as they are managers in the implementation of inclusive education in their respective schools.

III. DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

The aim of the study is to reveal factors that impedes excellence in the implementation of inclusive education in full service schools in Matlosana local education office. From the discussion with participants it was made clear that educators demonstrated misunderstanding of the Screening, Identification, Assessment and Support strategy. The misunderstanding can be ascribed to the kind of training educators received. The training lacked in–depth content and practical demonstration. Recommendations on the content and the dynamics of the training process are made. The overarching recommendation on the dynamics of the training indicated that the training should be revisited for improved methods of training.

The findings in the study also revealed that majority of teachers felt that for successful implementation of inclusive education, teachers need supportive leadership. Therefore it is pivotal that school management be empowered in the implementation of inclusive education. This findings were concurred by (Engelbrecht, 2020) who alluded that school management team influence the implementation of inclusive education when they provide support. This in a way imply that teachers need support from their supervisors regarding the implementation of inclusive education and identification of learners with learning barriers.

On the other hand principals outlined that support that they receive from the district based support team (DBST) is not sufficient as at times they receive training one or two times a year. Principals lamented that receiving very few training per year does not sufficiently capacitate them to deal with barriers that learners with learning barriers are having. It was also made evident that there are SBST in schools but most of the member are no more interested as they do not know their roles. Thus make the entire team functional. School based support in many schools are established but because they do not know their roles it ended up being the responsibility of SBST coordinators responsibility to make sure that inclusive education is catered for.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study intended to explore factors impeding the implementation of inclusive education in full service schools in Matlosana local education office. The study outlined few factors that hindered the implementation of inclusive education, *inter alia* inappropriate implementation of Screening identification and assessment and support (SIAS) policy, lack of functionality of School based support team (SBST), lack of teacher training, teachers failing to apply for learner concession and accommodation and placement, inadequate support and resources, as well as lack of curriculum adjustment.

It was concluded that all the stipulated challenges hampering the implementation of inclusive education be attended to in order to have successful and functional full service school that will enhance the identification of LSEN. Therefore, the Ministry of Education, teachers, school management team, and district based support team and all other stakeholders are encouraged to study these observed results and strive to devise solutions that ensure that inclusive education is achieved.

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